

A Study on the Difference between Organizational Learning And Learning Organization

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ABSTRACT : *When it comes to organizational learning and learning organization, people tend to confuse the two concepts of organizational learning and learning organization, and many scholars even think that they are the same thing. Although the two are closely related, there are essential differences between the two. The article starts with the research on the definition of organizational learning and learning organization, and further explores the differences and connections between the two. The results show that organizational learning is a dynamic process in terms of content, and learning organization refers to a form of organization ; From the perspective of the learning subject, the subject of organizational learning is the group, and the learning subject of the learning organization includes individuals, teams, and organizations.*

KEYWORDS - *Organizational learning, Learning organization*

I. INTRODUCTION

The learning organization theory is a new management theory that emerged in the 1990s. Many management scientists and organization theorists have actively explored this theory. Among them, Dr. Senge, a professor at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology in the United States The proposed fifth discipline of the learning organization has aroused strong response in management circles (Senge, 2014). However, the concept and research scope of organizational learning and learning organization are still vague. Most scholars believe that organizational learning and learning organization are interchangeable and are synonymous. The concepts of organizational learning and learning organization include all organizational changes and key concepts and issues between organizational work. Most of the definitions present a holistic rather than a difference between basic concepts. In order to enhance the scientific understanding of learning organization theory and better guide practice, it is necessary to identify, sort out and interpret its core concepts, and to clarify the relationship between organizational learning and learning organization by examining the core concepts of learning organization differences and connections (Spicer, & Sadler-Smith, 2006).

II. THE CONCEPT OF ORGANIZATIONAL LEARNING

Many scholars have discussed the meaning and significance of learning organization, and put forward different opinions. The following list is listed for comparative research. Among them, representative scholars include Senge, 2006; Marsick & Watkins, 2003; Marquardt, 2002; 1996; Garvin, 1993 and so on.

First of all, it is believed that the core concept of learning organization is innovation and change in order to adapt to development. Senge (2006) believes that: the promotion of learning organizations is to hope that organizations can produce fundamental changes, and this change combines the internal changes of people's values, mental models, desires, and behaviors, as well as external changes in strategies, structures, and system procedures. change. Therefore, the learning and change defined by the learning organization is a change from inner thinking to outer action. Watkins & Marsick (2003) also believes that an important feature of a learning organization is that it can enable the organization to change or transform. The connotations of specific changes include (Senge,2012): individual and team-level learning skills, awareness and sensitivity to the environment, attitude and value; and organizational-level leading concepts and innovation in the basic structure, as well as providing learning and improvement Theories, methods and tools. Summarizing Senge's view, he believes that: a learning organization is an organization that focuses on learning, disseminating, and innovating knowledge under the guidance of a common goal by the main members of a certain organization or a group. It is an organization with a high degree of cohesion and vigorous vitality. This organization is to give full play to the

creativity of each employee, and strive to form a learning atmosphere permeating the group and the organization. With learning, individual values are realized and organizational performance is greatly improved. In a learning organization, everyone can continuously break through the upper limit of their abilities, create results that are sincerely desired, cultivate new, forward-looking and open thinking methods, make every effort to achieve a common vision, and continue to learn how to learn together.

Secondly, it is believed that the learning organization is a process that promotes the acquisition, creation, application and transformation of organizational knowledge. Garvin (1993) pointed out: "A learning organization refers to an organization that is good at acquiring, creating, and transferring knowledge, and is guided by new knowledge and new insights, and has the courage to modify its behavior." Crossan & White (1999) systematically solve problems, adopt new methods for experimentation, learn from his own past practice, learn from the experience and good practice of others, and quickly and effectively transfer knowledge in the organization as the cornerstone of a learning organization. Engström & Käkelä (2019) believes that learning organizations: "experiment more, encourage more attempts, and allow more failures. They know a lot of information at any time, they are good at creating, acquiring and transmitting knowledge, and they are good at modifying to obtain new ones. Think of it as a human-centered management philosophy."

Cultivate the organizational learning ability of the members of the organization. Collinson, & Cook (2007) pointed out that a learning organization is an organization that promotes individual and group learning. It teaches members the ability to think critically to understand what should be done and why. It helps the organization learn from success and failure. As a result, he can recognize changes in the environment and make effective adaptations. The learning organization gives members the ability to generate new knowledge, new production and new services, so that production and service reach a new level. And Argyris & Schön (1997) pointed out: "From a systematic point of view, a learning organization is an organization that can effectively carry out collective learning and continuously improve its ability to collect, manage and use knowledge to achieve success." Bowen & Ware (2006) believe that learning organization is not only the learning of ability, but also the learning of learning. In other words, the learning organization not only has the ability to be competent in the environment, but also can continue to maintain this competent ability. Kim (1993) believes that learning organizations refer to those organizations that consciously encourage organizational learning to continuously enhance their learning capabilities; non-learning organizations allow organizational learning to be left to their feet, thereby gradually weakening their learning capabilities. Brix (2017) believes that a learning organization refers to an organization that can continuously learn, use systems thinking to engage in various experiments and solve problems, thereby enhancing personal knowledge and experience and changing the entire organization's behavior. Strengthen organizational change and innovation capabilities. Learning organization refers to an attitude and philosophy about what the organization is and the role of employees. In a learning organization, everyone recognizes and solves problems so that the organization can continuously experiment and improve, thereby enhancing the organization's capabilities.

III. THE CONCEPT OF LEARNING ORGANIZATION

"Learning" originally describes the behavior of an individual. Therefore, using "learning" to describe an organization's behavioral imagination is a kind of simulation. That is to use the way of describing individual behaviors to vividly describe an organizational behavior, showing a holistic learning behavior and weave learning (Dixon, 1994). Organizational learning from the perspective of individual perception. From this perspective, it can be seen metaphorically that the process of collective learning is seen to be similar to the process of individual learning (Garvin & Gino, 2008), for example: information Cognitive ability, comprehensive understanding ability, storage capacity and resilience (Harris & Jones, 2018). The key word "learning" of learning organizations refers to individual learning, and more emphasis is placed on purposeful learning, and how to recognize and purposeful learning, because of the different perspectives of people's problems, there are many ways to define organizational learning.

The first to propose the concept of organizational learning was Harvard University professors Argyris & Schon, In 1977, they published an article "Double-loop Learning in Organizations" in the Harvard Business Review. They first proposed and initially defined The concept of "organizational learning", "Organizational

Learning: A Theory of Action Perspective” by Argyris & Schon in 1978, which defines organizational learning as “the process of discovering and correcting errors.” Formally defined the concept of organizational learning and divided the types of organizational learning (Argyris & Schon, 1978). He believed that organizational learning was achieved through the learning of organizational members.

Now: “Individual learning activities are also affected by a similar social-ecological system composed of various elements. We call the system composed of these elements an organizational learning system”(Argyris & Schon, 1978). This can be summarized as the system and behavioral viewpoint of organizational learning.

Fiol & Lyles (2005) believe that organizational learning is a process of improving action through better knowledge and understanding. Garvin believes that organizational learning is a kind of activity, which includes five contents: solving problems systematically, learning from one’s own past and experience, learning from others, and promoting the diffusion of knowledge within the organization. DuFour & Eaker (1998) believed that organizational learning is formed by sharing information, knowledge, and spiritual models and based on past knowledge and experience. Field (2020) is defined as based on a specific cultural background, an enterprise revolves around its specific business activities to establish and perfect organizational routines and supplementary knowledge, to improve routine procedures, through this approach can improve the skills of employees and improve the efficiency of the organization To strengthen the adaptability and competitiveness of enterprises. Hughes (2001) believes that organizational learning occurs in the process of the organization through information processing to improve and improve the organization's potential behavior. Organizational learning can improve the quality of information sharing, communication, understanding, and decision-making in the organization (Jackson, 2000). Organizational learning can be seen as an enterprise that promotes knowledge innovation or knowledge acquisition and spreads it throughout the organization, embodying its capabilities in products, services, and systems (Lau & Chung, 2019). Organizational learning refers to the various actions an organization takes around information and knowledge in order to form its core competitiveness. It is a process in which the organization constantly strives to change or redesign itself to adapt to a continuously changing environment. It is an innovation process. It includes individual physical learning, team learning, whole-organization learning, and inter-organization learning (Lerer & Peysakhovich, 2017). These can be summarized as the viewpoints of information processing and knowledge management of organizational learning.

IV. THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL LEARNING AND LEARNING ORGANIZATION

The two terms of organizational learning and learning organization With the deepening of the study of learning organization, people gradually recognize the difference between the two concepts. From the general specification, organizational learning is descriptive and large multi-processing the learning process in organizations, organizational learning focuses on academic theories rooted in social and cognitive psychology. In practice, the focus of a learning organization is a special type of prescriptive regulations, which requires activities and is the effect of hard work (Montes & Haselbach, 2006). Organizational learning is an activity that describes a certain type of activity in an organization, while a learning organization refers to a specific type of descriptive organization and its own type. The learning organization is where learning occurs and promotes an organization. Learning would transform from individual learning to group learning between group or organizations, and it will lead to changes in behavior. If it does not result in a change in behavior, no real transformation has occurred.

From the perspective of goals, organizational learning emphasizes the management, training, knowledge and skills acquisition of human resources, while learning organizations emphasize organizational learning, and the purpose is to create a working environment that guarantees and supports learning for all employees. And organizational learning culture. From the perspective of content characteristics, organizational learning is an activity process, and learning organization is a form of organization that represents an organizational philosophy. From the perspective of the main body of learning, organizational learning is based on team learning, while learning organization is the full learning of individuals, teams and organizations. Organizational learning is a necessary condition for an organization to become a learning organization, not a sufficient condition.

In this sense, economist Martin Solomon (2005) commented: If the learning organization is regarded as an ideal model based on a large number of organizational behavior concepts in the past, it will help to better understand what a learning organization is. No organization has ever been or will have all the characteristics of a learning organization. Therefore, the learning organization should be regarded as the goal of struggle, rather than a realistic description of organizational structure activities.

V. CONCLUSION

Individual learning, organizational learning, and learning organization are three closely related concepts. Individual learning is the basis for building a learning organization. Any form of learning is ultimately completed by individuals; Organizational learning is the systematic integration of individual learning. An organization that everyone learns is not necessarily organizational learning. Organizational learning is a team learning form that shares a common mental model with the goal of the organization as the core; learning organization is the learning guiding philosophy and goal of organizational learning. A learning organization is an organizational form of an organization, a belief, and organizational learning is a component of the specific embodiment of a learning organization, and it is a necessary condition rather than a sufficient condition.

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